

TEACHING GRAMMAR, CLT versus GTM

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Abstract:

Teaching grammar effectively in ESL classes has always been a debatable issue among English instructors. There have been so many approaches among which CLT and GTM are the core topic of this article. By this research, I would like to know whether Communicative approach really works or not in the class as well as identifying its strong and weak sides. There are 3 main research questions which need to be answered through the journey of this article.

1. Can communicative approach really replace traditional grammar translation method?
2. What are the benefits and drawbacks of communicative approach in the classroom?
3. How much will it be effective when it is compared to using only one method?

KEY WORDS: Communicative language teaching, grammar translation method, quantitative method, inductive teaching/deductive teaching.

Introduction: It is undeniable that a lot of effort has been put into teaching english grammar effectively so far. Traditionally, Grammar translation method was considered to be the most common one that was applied for the class to improve learners' grammar skills. Even, 10 -15 years ago, It was in the core of the teaching process. Grammar rules are explained in the mother tongue and students are required to memorize and reproduce them. The role of a teacher is controller, being dominant. Students do whatever their teacher says. Somehow, this method works well in terms of understanding reading materials and being aware of grammar structures in them. Despite the fact that grammar translation method is good for those who wants to learn the language deeply, It brought so many

disadvantages as well. There was nothing to do with this method in terms of communicative language. Students who have been taught by this method may know very complicated grammar rules, structures like causative, subjunctive mood, inversion. They can easily understand and translate the sentences including these grammar structures. Nevertheless, they are unable to use them orally, in communication. This is the main problem concerning with that method. Clearly, what is needed is to find out ways of teaching grammar where learners not only can master a particular grammar topic but also they will be encouraged to use them communicatively. I would like to highlight one thing that my research topic is not new. It has been investigated by a lot of researchers so far. For ex: Richards and Rogers (2010)"language learning is best served when students are interacting, completing a task, learning content or resolving real life issues as the goal of language is to develop communicative approach") ,Noam Chomsky, Micheal Halliday, Anh, 2013; Canh, 1999, Henry widowson, Dell hymes and Bachman. My case study would be helpful for teachers who are struggling teaching their students with communicative grammar. Because by this research, we focus on both sides of communicative approach and how can it be effective in the classroom and whether it could replace translation grammar method or not.

II LITERARURE REVIEW

There has been much debate on teaching grammar through grammar translation method and communicative approach. Traditionally, grammar was considered as prescriptive, that is by telling people what rules they should know and how they should speak and write and this includes many aspects of linguistic knowledge. But the teaching of grammar for the past decades has undergone a substantial change in people's traditional attitudes and approaches. Today, more and more teachers as Celce-Murcia (1991, p. 460) have begun to focus the spoken English and discourse structure, making out between language use and language usage. Newby (2003) managed to sort things out by presenting three general ways of

approaching grammar throughout ELT history: traditional grammar teaching, communicative language teaching and post-communicative approaches.

1. Traditional Grammar Teaching

According to Doughty and Williams (1998), traditional grammar focuses on the learning of technical vocabulary for nouns, verbs, adverbs and adjectives; learners are taught grammatical rules to master sentence patterns. It means at classroom level that, a teacher explicitly presents to students a grammar rule followed by a practice exercise to apply the rule. The chance of drawing an incorrect form of the language is then minimized. Ellis (1995) and Larsen-Freeman (1991) discovered that this type of language learning, despite its facilitative effects stands less chance of impacting on language acquisition whereas for Ulrich (1994) the teaching of grammar should include three components: language structure, meaning and use. In fact, an important characteristic of traditional language teaching is that not much or even no emphasis is put on learners' communicative needs in real life situations but rather on their classroom immediate needs or just to satisfy exams demand. In Benin, the classroom teaching has unfortunately been more exam-oriented than catering for students meaningful practice. As a result, learners often have difficulty using what they have learned beyond the classroom setting. It is for this reason that Skehan (1996) is of the view that though mechanical practice may be of little help to effective grammar use, precise focus on a particular form can benefit students. However, it seems wise not to radically discard the traditional methodology but to combine it with the new communicative teaching methodology for all they can offer the CBA in a roundabout way.

2. Communicative Language Teaching (CLT) The CLT which appeared in the eighties has changed the world of foreign language teaching and has gone beyond linguistic theories. Richards (2006, p.23) contends that "It describes a set of general principles grounded in the notion of communicative competence as the goal of second and foreign language teaching. A

new approach that has evolved as our understanding of the processes of second language learning has developed.” Lopez & Agullo (2013) argued that the main objective of CLT is to teach communicative competence, which includes the knowledge of the construction blocks of sentences (e.g. parts of speech, tenses), a teaching methodology which refers to some aspects of language such as making use of language for various purposes and functions, varying them in taking account of the setting and the audience for instance, differentiating between formal and

informal, written and spoken discourse etc.

Communicative Grammar (CG)

Highlighting the role of grammar within the CLT can be controversial because some researchers that it does not include any grammar but has an exclusive focus on meaning while others think it still encompasses a strong grammar basis made of incorporated grammatical points. Thornbury (1999, p.18-19) to clear up the misconception distinguished two main types of approaches to CLT: the shallow-end approach and the deep-end approach. The former, encourages the use of communicative language through grammatical rules and their application in situation. In fact, it is an inductive way which does not make use of rote-learning of grammatical rules but rather encourages teachers to provide examples from which learners infer rules. Rutherford (1996) calls it consciousness-raising. The latter, the deep-end approach to CLT refers to the unconscious acquisition of grammar in communicative contexts without any previous and explicit teaching. This approach is in line with Krashen’s theory (1985) of Natural Approach. Unfortunately, this model proves inadequate as learners’ competence suffers from lack of accuracy and fluency and most teachers feel uncomfortable not to teach grammar for communicative purposes. To overcome this dichotomy, post-communicative approaches researchers such as Skehan (1998), contended for the integration of both models by arguing that conscious knowledge can become unconscious and vice versa.

Research methodology

The study applies quantitative research method. This research contains 2 tests, Pre and post test including 4 sections.

1. grammar test
2. writing
3. listening
4. speaking

The grammar pre test was taken first before teaching the students in order to know their levels. Following this, written oral exam were also taken based on 10 questions which require using relative clause and passive voice, causative. It was done by both groups on the same day, with researcher's visitation. Next, the two groups were taught with different methods: Student B and C with a communicative approach (the experimental members) and Student A with traditional grammar-translation method(the control member.) during the research period, 4 week lessons are observed in both students. Finally, A grammar post-test was given to both groups again on the same day, with researcher's visitation and after the test Oral exam was taken again to know if there were some changes on their competence skills or not. **RESEARCH TOOL.** Test was chosen as well as semi-structured interview as research tools. The reason why I chose 4 types of tools is to know their grammar both orally and written. I was going to identify that whether they could use the grammar structures orally as well as in written form or not. The strength of this type of research tool is to know the students real grammar and communicative knowledge at the same time. The tests and the questions on the oral exam were adopted from Cambridge tests.

TYPES OF TESTS	STUDENT A	STUDENT B	STUDENT C

GRAMMAR	2-10	2-10	3-10
LISTENING	2-10	1-10	2-10
WRITING	1-5	0-5	1-5
SPEAKING	1-5	1-5	1-5

Analysis and Results

1. PRE TEST.

The aim of this test was to compare the two groups in the amount of grammar, level of knowledge and ability to write communicative sentences with appropriate grammar. The second purpose is to know their real current level in terms of 5 grammar topics. The test was taken in 4 directions. And I called it Section A , Section B , Section C and Section D.

In Section A , 3 students were provided with 10 tests, based on 4 grammar topics such as passive voice , Reported speech, conditional type 2 and causative. In tests , Students were required to choose one from 4 options as it was multiple questions.

In Section B aimed to check the participants' writing skills by having them create complete sentences to form a letter. The letter consisted of 8 sentences using the above given 4 topics.

In Section C students should answer 5 questions orally.

In section d students are required to fill in the gaps by listening

Figure 1. Pre-test scores Student A student B and student C

In pre test , Students' results almost the same and showed rather lower figures in all sections.

However, in grammar student C found a little more than the 2 others.. All of them showed lower results when it comes to their levels. On the whole, no great

differences existed between the 3 students' pre-test scores for the selected research participants. That is, the experimental and control students performed the test rather equally.

POST -TEST

After weeks of lessons, Both groups were given a post-test again including 4 steps, grammar test, writing speaking and listening. The post-test aimed to check the knowledge the 3 members had acquired and their ability to express communicative sentences using appropriate grammar both orally and written form. The structure of post-test was almost the same as the previous one.

Section A and B assessed the students' ability in writing, using the correct forms of the given themes. Section C is aimed at checking their communicative skills using appropriate grammar structures. Section A includes 10 grammar tests on causative, reported speech, Conditional type 2 and passive voice. The test is in form of multiple choice, students are required to choose one of four. Section B requires students to write letter including 8 sentences using above given 4 grammar topics. Section C is an oral exam where 5 different questions are asked which require answers including causative, passive voice, conditional type 2 and reported speech.

Post test results

TYPES OF TESTS	STUDENT A	STUDENT B	STUDENT C
GRAMMAR	9-10	8-10	9-10
LISTENING	2-10	8-10	8-10
WRITING	1-5	5-5	4-5
SPEAKING	3-5	4-5	4-5

Figure 2 presents the average scores of 3 participants in each section. From this, it can be seen that The student A who was taught based on traditional

translation grammar method showed higher scores in terms of the two tests, grammar and writing than Student B and C who were taught based on communicative approach. Nevertheless, Student B and C showed higher figures in oral exam And listening when it is compared the previous one. I think this is because, the second group, student B and student C had an access to have tasks based on all four skills while learning grammar. What I meant is they were exposed to listening , speaking and writing at the same time while having a grammar theme. But student b only learnt grammar in translation grammar method without being exposed other skills.

The procedure of 4 week lesson in communicative approach.

Week 1 Topic was Passive voice .

- Introduction of the passive voice through listening a text of a conversation between supervisor and her employee(individual task)
 - read a text and underline passive forms of tenses without explaining the rules.(pair work)
 - Discovery of the forms, meaning and use through listening script (group work)
- Activities in the classroom: Information gaps with a given written text(pair work)
- Discussions to figure out solutions to Global warming(group work)

Week 2 The topic was Reported speech.

- Introduction of through listening text in which a person reported a story to her mother and direct speech through reading a text for later comparison. (individual work.
 - read the text and identify reported statements workout explanation of the rules.
- Activities : Role play in the form of a game for transmitting giving information (group work).
- Game of real information transmission.

week 3. the topic was Conditional type 2.

- Introduction of unreal condition in the present through a listening test (with a task) of a survey for the

(individual work)

- Discovery of the form, meaning and use through the listening script.

Activities: Oral interaction with a imaginary questions with unreal conditions(pair work) And to present his partner's answers.

Week 4. The topic was causative

-- Introduction of causative through a listening text conversation between the manager and secretary.(individual task)

-- Discovery of the form , meaning through the listening script. (pair work.)

Activities: Information gaps with a given text(pair work)

- a game for making causative sentences orally without mistakes. (group work)

The procedure of 4 week lesson in translation grammar method.

Week 1 The topic was passive voice.

- Introduction of passive voice rules through explanation by a teacher on the whiteboard

- Students are given exercise related to passive voice. (individual work)

Students read exercise aloud and at the same time A teacher checks.

- students are given homework related to this topic.

Week 2 The topic was reported speech.-

- Introduction of the topic by explaining the rules. And writing them on the whiteboard by a teacher.

- students were given a text and made them read each sentence one by one and translate it into Uzbek.

- Homework was given in the form of exercises.

Week 3. The topic was Conditional type 2

- Introduction of the topic by explaining the rules. And writing them on the whiteboard by a teacher.

- students were given a text and made them read each sentence one by one and translate it into Uzbek.

- Homework was given in the form of exercises.

Week 4. The topic was Causative

- Introduction of the topic by explaining the rules. And writing them on the whiteboard by a teacher.
- students were given a text and made them read each sentence one by one and translate it into Uzbek.
- Homework was given in the form of exercises.

What are the benefits and drawbacks of communicative approach in the classroom??

There a lot of assets of communicative approach from the data analyzed in the research.

Firstly, It allows learners not only learn grammar , but also making use of it at the same time both orally and in written form. In the communicative approach grammar is learnt unconsciously (Krashen's theories, 1985).another benefit of it can be seen in terms of lesson design. Lessons in communicative approach is more interesting and engaging when it is compared to traditional one.Students became so engaged and active as it is student-centered approach.Students in traditional method depend on teachers and less communicate with their partners. Can communicative approach really replace traditional grammar translation method? The answer is yes. It can replace the traditional grammar translation method. All in all, I have found answers to my questions. There are advantages of communicative methods in terms of acquiring all 4 skills. Learners who access to CLT can improve all of their skills at the same time. They will be able to put into practice what they have learnt in grammar rather than not be able to use them orally. Like other studies, this research paper has also got some limitations, which need further in-depth research. First, I only conducted research on 3 students. One in TGM AND THE OTHER 2 IN CLM. That's why I would recommend to have an experiment on more students in order to have more reliable results. If more students are attracted into the research, we will have an opportunity to check them following more unbiased outcomes. The other limitation is the

teaching process lasted only one month. It would be better if the experiment period were prolonged where we will have a good chance of having better results as well. There are also some disadvantages of communicative approach into teaching grammar in terms of time and labor. This approach is really time-consuming. As it aims at improving all skills of learners, teachers are required to allow students more time than the other grammar methods. It also exhausts both teachers and learners. Another drawback is its labor intensive property. Teachers who are intending to use this method are required to spend more energy and work harder than ever before. The reason is teachers should prepare needed materials based on the theme. However, one asset of it is it helps teachers to get more sophisticated in their own sphere. Despite some minus sides of CLT, its advantages outweigh everything. However, I would recommend you to integrate both CLT AND GTM into one lesson. Then we would have more effective grammar lessons. By this research what I wanted to prove that students' all four skills should be improved alongside with their grammar skills. While teaching grammar teachers should focus on practice more. Are students be able to use what they have learnt in grammar in practice? Can they put them into practice or not? We do pay attention to this aspects, then we can save our time and help students to master the English language in a very proficient way.

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